

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Neutralized Phenyl Phosphonous Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate (III)

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Neutralized phenyl phosphonous acid is oxidised by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) in the presence of osmium (VIII). The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III) is found to be independent of the initial concentration of oxidant but directly proportional to the concentrations of reducing substrate, hydroxyl ion and osmium (VIII). The results indicate that the oxidation of the substrate proceeds via the formation of a complex between reducing substrate (VI) and osmium (VIII) which then reacts with hydroxyl ion followed by a fast reaction between osmium and hexacyanoferrate (III). The activation parameters have been evaluated.

THE kinetics of the oxidation of some inorganic and organic compounds by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied by several investigators¹⁻¹⁰. In most cases, the reactions are extremely slow or do not proceed in the absence of catalyst but the addition of a catalyst like osmium (VIII) hastens the rate of reaction considerably. A search for literature reveals, therefore, that the reaction between alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) and phenyl phosphonous acid has not been studied although systematic kinetic investigations of the same substrate with other metal ions¹¹⁻¹³ have been reported earlier. The present paper therefore, deals with the kinetics of the oxidation of sodium salt of phenyl phosphonous acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III). The reaction was studied in the presence of osmium (VIII) since the reaction is too slow to be studied in the absence of added catalyst.

Experimental

Reagents : All inorganic materials except osmium (VIII) were of BDH (AnalaR) grades and used without further purification. A standard solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) was prepared by accurate weighing and its actual strength was checked by usual titration procedure. The details of the preparation of phenyl phosphonous acid and its estimation have been described elsewhere¹¹. Neutralized phenyl phosphonous acid was used for studying the reaction. The solution of osmium tetroxide (Johnson & Mathey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in the solution of potassium hydroxide. Freshly prepared sodium carbonate-sodium bicarbonate buffer was used during kinetic runs.

Procedure : The rate of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III) was followed spectrophotometrically by measuring optical density of the solution using a cell of path length 1 cm at 420 nm at which the oxidant shows maximum absorption. A Beckman DU model spectrophotometer was used. The initiation of reaction was carried out by mixing the requisite quantity of substrate maintained at a constant temperature into the solution

of oxidant, buffer and osmium (VIII). The plot of optical density against time is linear and the slope of each line gives initial rate (k_0). Each run was carried out in duplicate and the reproducibility was better than $\pm 1\%$. The rate of loss of initial oxidant was followed upto 70% conversion of initial hexacyanoferrate (III). The experimental set up has been described elsewhere¹¹. All the runs were taken in the presence of buffer and pH of the solution was adjusted to 10 unless otherwise mentioned.

Results

Stoichiometry : The sodium salt of the reducing substrate was mixed with large excess of hexacyanoferrate (III), buffer and osmium (VIII) and the mixture allowed to stand for 24 hr. It was observed that 2.0 equivalents of oxidant was consumed according to the equation.

Effect of reactant concentrations : The order with respect to each reactant was determined from the measurement of initial rates of reaction by keeping the concentration, in turn, fixed in one case and varying the other. During the variation of rate with the concentration of hexacyanoferrate (III), the concentrations of reducing substrate and catalysts were kept fixed at $2.75 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ respectively but the concentration of initial oxidant was varied between the limits $(2.52-6.05) \times 10^{-4} M$. The plots of optical densities against time are linear for various initial oxidant concentrations (Figure 1). The values of k_0 , which have been calculated are recorded in Table I and indicate that the rate is independent of initial hexacyanoferrate (III) ion. Again, when the concentrations of reducing substrate were varied from $(1.0-3.0) \times 10^{-2} M$, the initial hexacyanoferrate (III) and catalyst concentrations were adjusted to $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $11.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ respectively for each run. The values of initial rates along with the quotients, $\frac{k_0}{[PhPO_2H]^{0.5}}$ at

Fig. 1. Variation of initial rate with change in hexacyanoferrate (III) concentrations. $[\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}^-] = 2.75 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{Os(VIII)}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\text{pH} = 10.2$, $\text{Temp.} = 30.5^\circ$. $[\text{Hexacyanoferrate (III)}] = 2.52 \times 10^{-4}$, 3.53×10^{-4} , 4.54×10^{-4} , 5.5×10^{-4} and $6.05 \times 10^{-4} M$ for curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively.

various substrate concentrations are summarised in Table 2. The rate is, therefore, proportional to the concentration of reducing substrate.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE WITH THE CONCENTRATION OF HEXACYANOFERRATE (III)

$[\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}^-] = 2.751 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{Os(VIII)}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\text{pH} = 10.2$, and $\text{Temp} = 30.5^\circ$

$[\text{Hexacyanoferrate (III)}] \times 10^4 M$	2.52	3.53	4.54	5.54	6.05
$k_0 \times 10^2 (\text{mole min}^{-1})$	1.54	1.50	1.54	1.59	1.55

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE CONCENTRATION ON k_0

$[\text{Hexacyanoferrate (III)}] = 5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{Os(VIII)}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\text{Temp} = 35^\circ$

$[\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}^-] \times 10^2 M$	1.00	2.25	2.50	2.75	3.00
$k_0 \times 10^2 (\text{mole min}^{-1})$	0.585	1.37	1.52	1.64	1.73
$k_0 / [\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}^-] (\text{min}^{-1})$	0.580	0.609	0.608	0.600	0.575

Effect of hydroxyl ion concentration on the initial rate: The effect of hydroxyl ion concentrations on the initial rate was studied at constant reactant as well as

catalyst concentrations. The values of k_0 at various hydroxyl ion concentrations are recorded (Table 3) The $k_0 / [\text{OH}^-]$ values indicate that the rate is directly proportional to the initial OH^- ion concentration. Since the ionic strengths of the solution were high (0.12-0.17 M), no attempt has been made to calculate hydroxyl ion concentrations from activity coefficient corrections. Moreover, the above increase in rate was mainly due to the increase in hydroxyl ion concentration and not due to increase in ionic strength as because the rate has no influence at different ionic strengths of reaction mixture (0.13-0.17 M) maintained by the addition of potassium sulphate.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF HYDROXYL ION CONCENTRATION ON THE RATE AT 28°

$[\text{PhPO}_2\text{H}^-] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[\text{Hexacyanoferrate(III)}] = 5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[\text{Os(VIII)}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-4} M$

$[\text{OH}^-] \times 10^4 M$	0.398	1.00	1.58	2.82	5.01
$k_0 \times 10^3 (\text{mole min}^{-1})$	1.56	4.33	6.70	13.40	17.90
$k_0 / [\text{OH}^-] (\text{min}^{-1})$	39.2	43.3	42.3	47.5	35.8

Effect of catalyst concentration on the rate : The concentrations of both substrate and oxidant were adjusted to $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$ respectively. The catalyst concentrations were varied between the limits $(2.0-10.0) \times 10^{-5} M$. The rate of reaction is increased with the increase in catalyst concentration. The values of $k_0/[Os(VIII)]$ are found to be fairly constant indicating that the initial rate is also proportional to the catalyst concentration (Table 4).

The salt effects have also been studied for the other reaction. Potassium chloride increases the rate of reaction (Table 5) whereas the initial rate has no effect in potassium sulphate $(3.0-15.0) \times 10^{-4} M$ and a constant value of k_0 which is 1.32×10^{-4} (mole sec^{-1}) has been obtained. Consequently, the increase in rate in potassium chloride may be considered due to the increase in chloride ion concentration and not due to variation in ionic strength.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF CATALYST CONCENTRATIONS ON THE RATE AT 28°

$[PhPO_2H^-] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$

$[Osmium(VIII)] \times 10^5 M$	2.0	4.0	5.0	8.0	10.0
$k_0 \times 10^3$ (mole min^{-1})	1.11	1.92	2.27	4.21	6.11
$k_0/[Os(VIII)]$ (min^{-1})	55.5	48.0	38.0	54.1	61.4

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF SALT ON THE REACTION RATE

$[PhPO_2H^-] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-} = 5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$, $pH=10.2$, $Temp=31^\circ$

$[KCl] \times 10^3 M$	0	2.5	5.0	7.0	10.0
$k_0 \times 10^2$ (mole min^{-1})	1.07	1.70	1.82	2.59	3.30

Influence of temperature and the activation parameters : The temperature dependence of the reaction was studied at constant substrate, oxidant and catalyst concentrations of $3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ respectively. The initial rates were found to be 1.31×10^{-2} , 1.73×10^{-2} , 2.28×10^{-2} and 2.82×10^{-2} (lit. mole $^{-1}min^{-1}$) at 30, 35, 40 and 45°C respectively. The values of k_{sp} were estimated to be 4.37×10^{-1} , 5.76×10^{-1} , 7.60×10^{-1} and 9.40×10^{-1} (min^{-1}) at the respective temperatures. The plot of $\log k_{sp}$ against $1/T$ yields a straight line (Figure 2) from the slope of which energy of activation was calculated to be 9.7 ± 0.5 (kcal mole $^{-1}$). The other activation parameters, $\log PZ \Delta S^\ddagger$ and ΔG^\ddagger (308°K) have been estimated to be 4.81 ± 0.3 (sec^{-1}), 37.7 ± 1.6 (e.u.) and 21.2 ± 0.4 (kcal mole $^{-1}$) respectively. The large entropy change suggests that both the reacting species are charged.

Discussion

Paenyl phosphonous acid is easily oxidised by metal ions such as vanadium (V)¹¹, chromium (VI)¹² and manganese (III)¹³ in acid medium. The redox potentials of vanadium (V)→vanadium (IV), chromium (VI)→chromium (III) and manganese (III)→manganese

Fig. 2. Influence of temperature on the rate of reaction and the plot of $\log K_{sp}$ against $1/T$. $[PhPO_2H^-] = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Hexacyanoferrate(III)] = 5.04 \times 10^{-4} M$ and $[Os(VIII)] = 1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$.

(II) couples which are +1.0, +1.36 and +1.56 volts respectively are high enough to oxidise the substrate. The oxidation of the same substrate by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III), on the other hand, do not proceed in the absence of any added catalyst. This is possibly because the oxidation potential of ferrocyanide →ferricyanide couple which is very low (−0.36 volt) would not differ appreciably from that of phosphonous →phosphonic couple, the data for which is lacking in the literature. However, the oxidising or reducing capacity of a material can be altered diminishing the activity of the oxidised or the reduced form of the redox couple and this can be achieved by the addition of a suitable complexing agent. The catalyst osmium (VIII) which is necessary to promote the reaction, would possibly play part in lowering the redox potential of phosphonous →phosphonic couple. It is already known that in the oxidation of chromium (III) by persulphate and oxalic acid by permanganate, silver (I) and manganese (II) ions are used as catalysts for the respective reactions. The increase in the speed of the reaction in these cases is ascribed to the generation of higher valent species of metal ions such as silver (II) or silver (III) and manganese (III) as active intermediates which help the course of these reactions. In the present study, the catalyst, osmium (VIII) already remains in its highest oxidation state and the function of osmium (VIII) would be different. However, it was

claimed earlier by Krauss and Wilken^{14,15} that potassium salt of perosmic acid exists as $K_2[OsO_4(OH)_2]$. It was, later on, shown by Sandel et. al¹⁶ from spectrophotometric measurements in potassium hydroxide solution that osmium tetroxide yields a value of $\sim 10^{-10}$ for first dissociation constant at 25°. Consequently, although the exact composition of perosmic acid is not known, the anion may be designated as OsO_3H^- and not as $OsO_6H_2^{2-}$ since the second dissociation constant of the parent acid is even weaker ($\sim 10^{-15}$) than that of the first one. The hydroxo osmium (VIII) species like OsO_5H^- reacts with the reducing substrate to give complexes which may be designated by their structures (A) and (B). Figure 3 shows the u. v. spectra of osmium (VIII) with and without $PhPO_2H^-$. The latter does not absorb in this range at this low substrate concentration of $10^{-5}M$. Increase in optical density indicated a change of species which in this case is a complex between osmium (VIII) and $PhPO_2H^-$.

(A)

(B)

The complex (A) would result if active variety of the substrate reacts with osmium (VIII) and complex (B) would be formed if inactive variety of substrate is the reducing species. It has already been pointed out¹¹ that active form predominates only in the acid medium and inactive variety in alkaline medium. It is, therefore, suggested that complex (B) would take part in the reaction which reacts with OH^- ion to give phenyl phosphonium ion and osmium (VI) in the to slow step Osmium (VI) is finally oxidised by two molecules of hexacyanoferrate (III) regenerating osmium (VIII) and finally phenyl phosphonium ion gets converted to phenyl phosphonic acid.

Fig 3. Ultraviolet absorption spectra of osmium (VIII) with and without $PhPO_2H^-$

1, osmium (VIII) spectrum of concentration $5.0 \times 10^{-4}M$.

2, spectrum of the mixture of osmium (VIII) and $PhPO_2H^-$ where the substrate concentration is $5.0 \times 10^{-5}M$. Concentration of osmium (VIII) is the same as in 1.

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